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COLLABORATIVE DESIGN PROJECTS PROMOTING WORK-RELATED LEARNING IN ENGINEERING CURRICULA: FEEDBACKS FROM THE FIELD

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ABSTRACT

ISAE-Supmeca, a French engineering school, has chosen since decades to engage in work-related learning. In the framework of this orientation and as a part of a reflection on the enhancement of hybridization of teaching methods before and during the covid-19 era, our paper presents how collaborative design projects are used to promote work-related learning among students. This study aims to propose a critical analysis and a feedback of the use of Problem- and Project-Based Learning (PBL) and Collaborative Project-Based Learning (CPBL) in the engineer curriculum of ISAE-Supmeca students. Several educational research projects, carried out with partner institutions, have been providing frameworks for many students' projects, especially

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CPBL, for years. The originality of our study lies on the nature of the CPBL students' projects analyzed. Indeed, they involve students' teams from two different academic partners with different levels and backgrounds and can run during several semesters. The projects are collaborative, multi-partner and involve the need of a proper transmission from teams to other teams. The general framework is analyzed and three projects are observed in depth in order to highlight good practices. Our study identified six good practices in three topics: collaboration between the groups forming the whole project team, project management and digital chain management. The first goal of these good practices is to enable students to have an optimized learning experience in an environment as close as possible to real professional conditions. The second goal is to help practitioners (teachers, industrial partners) to improve their working methods.

1 INTRODUCTION

ISAE-Supmeca has been involved in educational research for a decade through concrete students' projects involving several stakeholders. We will here quote two of these projects: PLACIS (Collaborative Platform for Systems Engineering) and EXAPP_3D (Experiment Learning by Problems and Projects via 3D Design).

PLACIS was a large-scale project coordinated by ISAE-Supmeca and co-funded by the French National Agency for Research under "Investments for the future" program from 2012 to 2017. The project aimed at promoting active learning and teaching through industrial, international and at-a-distance collaborative projects, carried out by engineer students. PLACIS led to several theoretical questions and to the development of an Erasmus+ project (called EPICES) more dedicated to the role of teachers in Problem- and Project-Based Learning (PBL) and to assessment issues.

EXAPP_3D (Experiment Learning by Problems and Projects via 3D Design) is an ongoing so-called e-FRAN project coordinated by ISAE-Supmeca and co-funded by the French Fund Deposits, from September 2016 to December 2022. The project aims to promote active learning involving on common dedicated projects students from secondary school and/or high school and/or Bachelor's degree and/or engineering school. These projects focus on collaboration, conception, 3D design and lead to concrete deliverables.

Through these projects ISAE-Supmeca has gained experience on international and industrial multisemester collaborative projects (PLACIS) and on regional translevel multisemester collaborative projects (EXAPP_3D). PLACIS and EXAPP_3D allowed multisemester and even multiyear projects, some of these projects are still expanding through both frameworks. In this paper, we will focus on both of them.

Our study focuses on the feedback from ISAE-Supmeca's educational practices to implement and improve students' experience of learning through work. More specifically, the aim is to perform a critical study of the existing situation and capitalize on in order to draw good practices from the learning experience in the context of multi-stakeholder collaborative projects.

Our paper is organized as following. Section 2 provides insights into work-related learning practices through a literature review and outlines the context of their application at ISAE-Supmeca. Section 3 presents the specific projects analyzed in-depth in order to provide the feedback. Section 4 exposes the feedbacks and findings from the field. Finally, section 5 concludes and opens to a possible wider study.

2 WORK-RELATED LEARNING AT ISAE-SUPMECA, FROM PROJECTS TO COLLABORATIVE PROJECTS

According to Smith and Betts [1], there are three different ways to connect learning and work. We have learning about work, learning at work and learning through work. The use of business-based case studies is an example of learning about work. Learning through work is experiential, but not necessarily in the workplace [1]. Our paper focuses on learning through work according to this previous taxonomy. Also, for this study, we adopt the work-related learning definition presented by Kyndt and Baert [2] « as the engagement in formal and informal learning activities ... to acquire and/or improve competences (integrated knowledge, skills, and attitudes) that change individuals' present and future professional achievement (and eventually also their career) and organizational performance. »

The next section will present key literature elements related to our study and detail the ISAE-Supmeca students' projects context and frameworks.

2.1 Literature review: learning processes in collaborative students projects

The first step to optimize learning is to understand how it occurs. Understanding the way in which people acquire new knowledge and skills, understanding how these knowledge and skills can be changed, updated or enhanced are both fundamental issues. Shuell [3] claims that "...learning is an active, constructive, and goal-oriented process...". The second step is to design a supportive learning framework. In the learning process three criteria are unavoidable [3]. The first criterion is the change in an individual's behavior or ability. The second is practice or experience that produces the change. The third criterion is that the change is a lasting one.

Formal and informal learning are important components of the learning process [2]. Indeed, there is a continuum between both of them with greater purity at either end [4][2]. Despite being often presented in contrast [5] [6] [2], they should not be separated and can be complementary [2].

Formal learning is typically institutionally sponsored, classroom-based, and highly structured [6]. Informal learning is characterized by a low degree of planning [2]. It includes incidental learning [6]. Its outcomes are not defined in advance. They depend on the learning context, learning support, learning time and learning opportunities. The opportunities of learning are not restricted to intentionally created learning environments but can occur during several on- and off-work-related activities. Informal learning presents many benefits at work as flexibility, rapid transfer to practice and resolution of work-related problems [5]. During the informal learning process, students

gain knowledge and skills through their own self-engagement. They learn on their own and through interaction with others [7].

PBL approaches are perfect frame for both formal and informal learning. PBL approaches have been used for many decades [8]. These approaches place students at the center of the learning process [9][10]. Indeed, students are actively involved through prepared situations (problem-based learning) or real situations (project-based learning) [11]. They work to identify what they need to learn in order to solve a problem. To do so, they continually re-evaluate their approach in response to outcomes of their efforts. As a consequence, during the learning journey, students can acquire both content and thinking strategies [8]. In this journey, the teacher acts to facilitate the learning process rather than to provide knowledge.

PBL is familiar in engineering education with growing use in first-year engineering courses [11]. This popularity in engineering schools can be partially explained by the fact that PBL involves engineering students in a dynamics close to challenges and environments they are likely to encounter as professionals. Additionally, PBL fosters self-regulated learning, develops effective problem-solving skills [10], helps students become effective collaborators and enhances their motivation [8].

In a collaborative problem- and project-based learning (CPBL), the learning is fulfilled by the involvement of students in a collaborative group project. CPBL uses a production model [12]. The entire process is meant to mirror real world production activities. During the collaborative project, students' own ideas and approaches are used to accomplish different tasks.

At the beginning, the learners define the purpose for creating the end product and create a plan to the project management. As there is less centralization than in a pure PBL, management and share of information is a key element. During different steps of the project, students not only resolve problems and issues encountered, but they also really learn how to deal with a multiactors environment and how different kinds of stakeholders react. They go beyond the traditional soft skills and have to deal with the management of the information and of the engineering tools.

2.2 ISAE-Supmeca context

ISAE-Supmeca aims to train students not only to become classic engineers, but also to be able to understand multidisciplinary and industrial issues, to work in teams, with people from different cultures. More generally, ISAE-Supmeca prepares them to be actors of their curricula and to move easily in today's and tomorrow's work world. To achieve this goal, it is needed to establish a bond between education and work.

The approach adopted at ISAE-Supmeca aims to use its strong relationships with industrial companies in order to make the experience of students as close as possible to the future environment they will face in their work. So, one of the challenges is to have as much time as possible under conditions close to a professional context to create a real work-related experience. PBL is one of the most efficient learning approaches to create work-related experience. It allows to develop skills and

competencies linked to teamwork. Through interactions, formal and informal learning, students develop the ability to create, present and argue propositions.

ISAE-Supmeca, through PLACIS and EXAPP_3D frameworks, developed projects involving many stakeholders and reflecting the industrial reality. These projects create a framework allowing students to interact with counterparts working on different parts of the projects with different backgrounds in order to respond to a challenge.

Many student projects have been developed with several partners. Most of them included at least one professional partner and one academic partner (international at a Master level, or local at a Bachelor or lower level). Some of partners were far away geographically. Remote collaboration became then the normality.

The covid-19 pandemic added another challenge: the projects were carried out entirely remotely instead of partly remotely, due to health constraints. In our case, it is an evolution, making these projects more difficult, but this is not a full-scale revolution.

PLACIS and EXAPP_3D include the following types of projects:

- Basic projects: sometimes one-shot study, involving several partners but not planned to last several semesters with a heavy project management work,
- Complex projects: multi-semester project, with two academic partners having each a group of students working at least partly at the same period during a semester. A professional partner provides a real subject of study. The main features are: remote work, use of professional tools and everything being done in the way that can be defined as “the students change, the tutors stay, the institutions stay, the project runs”. Some projects were active during five years.

In our study, we are focusing on three complex projects, which are full CPBL projects as presented in section 2.1. Within them, students from ISAE-Supmeca and its partners work in groups and are involved in a greater team made of the groups of each institution plus the tutors (academic and professional), as shown in figure 1 hereafter.

Fig. 1. ISAE-Supmeca collaborative projects model

Fig. 2. ISAE-Supmeca collaborative learning process model

Figure 2 shows the steps of the learning process implemented in the projects. The students start with an initial body of knowledge and competencies. While facing issues in the project, students are led to develop strategies to make this body of knowledge grow. These strategies are often developed through formal and informal exchanges and pooling of expertise of different partners of the project. The implementation of these strategies triggers a learning-by-doing mechanism making it possible to capitalize on the experience.

3 PROJECTS DESCRIPTION AND OVERVIEW

In this section, we present an overview of the studied projects and their integration in the ISAE-Supmeca curriculum.

In our study, the students involved in the three considered projects are the 3rd year engineers (equivalent to Master 2) from ISAE-Supmeca and senior technician (equivalent to the 2nd year of bachelor) from Lycee Louis Armand (LLA). These projects took place in 2019-2020 (Mini-Bee) and 2020-2021 (all three projects).

More precisely, the Mini-Bee project consists of designing and prototyping a Vertical Take Off and Landing (VTOL) aircraft (an example of design of the Mini-Bee in TRL2 is presented in figure 3), launched in January 2015 by Technoplane. The vehicle has hybrid propulsion that uses electric motors with a thermal engine for urban air mobility. Having VTOL features, this allows the vehicle to have high mobility as a helicopter, but also a high cruising speed, with maximum weight and maximum budget specifications to be respected.

Fig. 3. Mini-Bee collaborative project: example of design in a taxi version (TRL2)

Eurlab's goal is to collaboratively create innovative robotic systems. RovDrone is one of its projects. It is a robotic system made up of a rover and a drone that can assist rescue teams in a disaster area or explore hard-to-reach sites. The rover must be able to move independently in an unfamiliar environment and provide video information, photos and terrain analysis to the user.

For the past two years, the introduction of foils (composed of a front wing, a stabilizer, a fuselage and a mast) on surfboards has opened up new development prospects for manufacturers. Several had the idea of using an electric thruster in order to be able to feel the sensations of flying over water without needing a wave to generate the necessary take-off speed. The challenge of the project is therefore to design the foil of the efoil system to reduce energy consumption in the given operating range.

What these three projects have in common is that they are carried out by a team made up of a mixture of groups of senior technical students and groups of engineering students. They also all have a third partner providing the subject, one (Eurlab) being a small lab created by European teachers and two being start-up companies. Another difference is that two projects are recent and involve only two academic actors, while one project (Mini-Bee) is a highly collaborative R&D project involving many academic actors (Lycee Louis Armand and ISAE-Supmeca are only two of them) lasting for years and coordinated by the start-up Technoplane SAS (which collaborative with ISAE-Supmeca since with agile methodology and an open share of technical information). The main features of these CPBL are presented in the table 1 hereafter.

Table 1. Main features of the projects studied

<i>Project name</i>	<i>Frameworks</i>	<i>Partners</i>
Mini-Bee	PLACIS & EXAPP_3D	Technoplane SAS, LLA, ISAE-Supmeca, among many other partners
RovDrone	EXAPP_3D	Eurlab project, LLA, ISAE-Supmeca
Efoil	EXAPP_3D	Company (confidential), LLA, ISAE-Supmeca

4 LESSONS LEARNED FROM THE FIELD

In this section, we presents the best practices identified in our study. They are based on the feedback on the projects performance collected through observation and interviews with both closed and open questions with academic supervisors coaching the projects (for all three projects, one tutor per institution), students and the industrial tutor from Technoplane SAS. The following qualitative in depth analysis has been adopted: study of the findings from the feedback, their nature and convergences into statements and ultimately the extraction of good practices related to the statements.

4.1 A rich feedback with clear statements

In our everyday lives, Information Technologies (IT) became more common and present in almost every part of our doings [13]. IT artifacts such as computers, software applications, and smartphones are everywhere [14]. Due to the covid-19 pandemic situation, the flow of projects that were already largely done remotely has witnessed heavy use of these digital artifacts.

The first statement is that the use of digital tools is more extended than never before. For example, nine tools (3DExperience, Catia V6, Teams, Wikimedia, file server on a private cloud, Zoom, Google Hangout, Dropbox, TeamViewer) are used in the Mini-Bee project because of its very complex nature and numerous actors. In projects, some tools were proposed by the students for convenience. Others were imposed by the institution or the company. As a consequence, the information may not be up-to-date in several digital spaces and/or at some moments and/or for some actors of the project. The industrial tutor from Technoplane highlighted that the use of the email also worsens the situation in some cases. Here comes the second statement, linked to the first one: there is a dispersion of the information.

But, as noticed by several respondents, even when there are many tools, there are reference tools, and sharing them is mandatory and should be respected. When it is, as noticed one of the academic tutors, no problem of file version or file format happens. He points out the need of “a computer-aided design tool integrated to a platform” in the case of these kinds of complex CPBL. Nevertheless, as noticed by an experienced 3DExperience user, collaborative engineering tools require a change in the behavior of new users (students therefore). They have to get acquainted with the existing information generated by other collaborators, work, produce documents related to this work, publish this work and share the information. To achieve this result, users must be trained in this process and in the tools (collaborative platforms) to facilitate this process. The training of these tools can be done remotely in interaction with a trainer but it is then necessary that the users force themselves in the collaboration process on a regular basis so that it becomes a habit. The context of the pandemic does not facilitate this because the training interactions were (and still are) limited and less rich. One tutor confirmed this difficulty for students with limited experience to “access (and use) the working areas in 3DExperience: 3DSpace, 3DDashboard, 3DDrive”. Consequently, some students prefer to use a non-integrated tool instead of an integrated tool, for example using “Dymola standalone instead of using Dymola within 3DExperience” because it is “faster, easier to use and does not require a lot of resources.” Acting in that way, they break the team work (only a small group is made of insiders, others become outsiders). This confirms and reinforces the second statement about the information dispersion stated above. On the other hand, when it is well done, “centralizing data for remote work teams makes it possible to better synchronize tasks and work on the right versions”. So, we are facing a behavior issue here and it is the third statement: it is hard to convince users to adapt their behavior to a degraded context, especially when the users are hundred percent online.

Before the pandemic, people met, at least in two ways during a CPBL: between groups during a kick-off meeting or a final presentation and among a group during all the project period. During the pandemic period, people do not meet between groups, but sometimes, do not even meet within the same group. It impacts negatively the interpersonal relations and creates communication problems. Our fourth statement is: people are more dispersed physically than never before.

Linked to the dispersion is the problem of common time to collaborate directly, i.e. working remotely but not fully in the asynchronous mode. As explained by one of the academic tutors, the solution was found without the tutors: “The major problem was to find time slots for both technician students with their supervisors on the one hand, and ISAE-Supmeca students with their supervisors on the other hand. However, the students were able to talk to each other when their supervisors were not available.” Here is our fifth statement: CPBL context urges students to work in autonomy.

So, the multiplicity of actors, tools and locations makes the project management and the centralization of results more difficult. Indeed, the project “runs faster than its formalization”, as claimed by one of the academic actors. As a consequence, the project management is at risk and harder. But, when well-organized and formalized

since the beginning of a semester for all its actors, apart from the problem of finding common time slots, using new tools like Teams makes it easy to organize meetings with students, especially unplanned ones. Several respondents affirm that it is “sometimes easier to plan remotely than face-to-face”. Also, “access to exchanges between students makes it possible to better supervise the work and to intervene as soon as possible”. Finally, “coaching and collaborative learning (peer coaching) help students in developing their skills”. These last remarks by a teacher make us conclude with our sixth statement, on project management: being agile is a must in order to fit with the evolution of tools and behaviors of students, but the autonomy has to be controlled to prevent overactivity and loss of control, very short regular meetings help.

4.2 A set of best practices

From the previously established statements and from the feedback of the PLACIS experience (kick-off meeting, formalization with industrial partners, clear requests for confidentiality...), we suggest hereafter a set of best practices (BP) composed of six good practices dealing with collaboration between groups, project management and digitalchain management:

- BP 1: Make the rules clear from the beginning! (tools, data management, way to work...)
- BP 2: Keep it lean: rationalize the number of collaborative tools!
- BP 3: Collaborate digitally, but stay human! (meet in-person if possible, and at least online at the beginning of the project and at specific milestones, especially when meeting within a group is not physically possible),
- BP 4: Take time to learn and improve the use of tools! (Go in-depth, especially for the complex tools, improve informal learning as much as possible, in a peer-to-peer fashion, which is a fair complement to a formal way done in person or online),
- BP 5: Manage the share of data! (from the beginning to the end of the project period, spell properly file names, integrate and contextualize data),
- BP 6: Empower students to make them autonomous! (keep the frame as large as possible, but maintain a frame requiring short and regular exchanges).

5 CONCLUSION

Our study led us to draw up six best practices. Their confluence point is project management, which tends to be the key in CPBL. Understanding who is who and who does what in this kind of project is difficult but needed. Defining a project manager and maybe an assistant is an interesting way to deal with the complexity of CPBL.

As summarized by an academic tutor, “collaborative work brings meaning and involvement to the complex and evolving issues faced by students” allowing awareness of their future professional environment. The covid-19 pandemic allowed “an acceleration of collaborative remote work”. The good practices identified in our study will be disseminated to enforce work-related learning for ISAE-Supmecca students. It will be done as part of a broader Initiative launched by the Educational Innovation Unit (EIU) of ISAE-Supmecca to capitalize on the pandemic experience.

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